

USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND RESEARCHING THEM

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the history, characteristics, and use of phraseological units, and researches on their use in English sentences are presented and analyzed with examples.

Key words: linguistics, speech, narrow and broad meaning, categorical symbols, literary studies, grammar, communicative function.

Introduction: Phraseological units – a combination of several words that are stable in composition. Therefore, when analyzing a phraseological unit, regardless of its type and the length of the words in it, it always appears as one member of the sentence. As a branch of linguistics, the main focus is on the study of phraseology and their categorical features, as well as on the determination of the laws of use of phraseology in speech. One of the biggest problems is to differentiate and separate phraseologisms from word combinations that are formed in speech (that is, not ready in advance) and to identify the signs of phraseology on this basis.

Main part: Phraseological units are usually understood in 2 types which are narrow and broad senses. When it is understood in a broad sense, the circle of phraseology includes proverbs and sayings, stable sentences characteristic of folklore, some forms of communication (greetings, farewell sentences). But the question of understanding phraseological units in a broad sense is still controversial. Phraseologisms are like a picture exhibition with examples of vivid and wonderful customs, traditions and fairy tales of peoples. Phraseology is not only the most diverse, but also the most democratic layer of dictionaries, and this layer is enriched mainly by means of “live” speech. Phraseology first appeared in literary studies. When translating a certain work from one language to another, it is impossible to translate the fixed word combinations exactly. Phraseologisms existing in those languages have been studied. The term phraseology was first used in world philology in 1558 by the English literary scholar Neander. He had to use this term while translating works of art. Although most of the phraseological materials are embodied in dictionaries and

other literature, scientific works on the theory of phraseology can also be found in the linguistic literature of Western Europe and America. Until recently, issues of English phraseology were studied within the framework of grammar, stylistics, lexicography and language history. In all languages, phraseology was studied as a part of lexicology. During the development of linguistics, phraseology was accepted as an independent branch of linguistics and is being studied. It should be noted that linguists from Russia and a number of other European countries have carried out many scientific studies on the study of English phraseology. Some positive results have been achieved.

Although the French linguist Charles Bally introduced the term phraseology to science, this term was reflected in the works of American and Western European linguists. According to the functions performed in the language, the phraseological units of English and Uzbek languages are divided into two large groups: phraseologisms with a communicative function and those without. Thus, phraseological units with a communicative function are divided into communicative and nominative ones. In order to determine the speech activity of phraseological units related to profession in English and Uzbek languages, 24 phraseological units made with the most common personal noun component of the English language are analyzed:

Baker: to spell the baker; baker's dozen; the butcher, the baker, the candlestick maker; pull devil pull baker

Builder: Jerry — builder

Busman: busman's holiday

Butcher: the butcher, the baker, the candlestick maker; butcher's bill, butcher's meat

Carpenter; such carpenters such chips

Cobbler : shoemaker: a cobbler must stick to his last, the shoemaker's wife is the worst shod; shoemaker's stock

Cook head c and bottle washer; son of the sea cook; too many cooks spoil the broth; every cook praises his own broth; God sends us meat and the devil sends cooks; cold cook

Driver: back-seat driver

Fisher: the great fisher of souls Hatter: mad as a hatter

Hewer: hewers of wood, drawers of water

Hunter: lion hunter; fortune hunter

Glazier: Is your father a glazier?

Labourer: the labourer is worthy of his fire; lalxmrrers in the vineyard

Navy. To work like a navy

Nurse: dry nurse; wet nurse

Potter: clay in the hands of the potter

Conclusion: To sum up, phraseology is used figuratively, figuratively, and has historical norms and methods of use, and their meaning is clarified in the course of a certain speech.

List of used literature:

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